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“EDUCATION, FREEDOM, AND GROWTH: AN AUTOBIOGRAPHICAL ESSAY”

“People at war with themselves will always cause collateral damage in the lives of those around them.”

John Mark Green

Early Influences

Growing up, I used to think that adults have the monopoly of knowledge and authority over the lives of their young ones. Dad was a strict disciplinarian so we see him as the sole authority at home. But that was when he decided to be with us for good – after living with another in a place far from us, his family.

I was born to parents whose love and understanding for each other became shaky when I was barely three months old. Mom brought me from Davao to Leyte when dad had his affairs with many different women after his business successfully took off.

One day, I saw mom with her suitcases and bags. Clingy as I was, I wanted to go with her. At 3 years old, all I wanted to see with my mom were trees that seemed to be moving when I'd be in a bus. A candy was already a heaven to me, too.

“Mom, I want to go with you. I don't want ice cream or candy. No. I want to ride in a bus,” I pleaded. But she brushed me off and said, “I'll just submit these papers. When I get home, I will bring many candies. Be good, okay? This will not take long”.

I was relieved believing in mom's words that she'd be home. I waited for her. One hour. Two hours. I fell asleep and woke up when it was dusk already. My aunt called me home and I saw my brothers and sisters in the same house. We were divided – one of my brothers was with my other aunt, and I, together with my elder sister, was with our childless aunt and uncle. It was too much to process. I couldn't understand what really happened until the following day when mom seemed to be nowhere to be found. I felt so deceived. From there I realized that adults are deceiving and that they don't live on what they promised. They hold the authority to either make or break your life (Dewey, 2001) as cited in (Palmer, 2006). This belief was proven to be true by my elementary teacher. For me, *to be in authority is to have the entitlement to have one's wishes acceded to*. I had been following orders from mom, aunt, uncle, and teachers. There was no option. I realized that to be an authority is to have knowledge which can be relied upon. Traditionally, parents and teachers have been thought to be authorities in both of these senses. I believed in them as the foundation of truth – of reliable truth. They have been thought to have the entitlement (and have been awarded the concomitant power) to ensure that their wishes are adhered to and they have been appointed partly because of their

possession of seemingly reliable knowledge to be imparted to their children and students. My parents seemed to have been in authority in breaking our lives, our dreams, our future. Well, at least, for me. I was five years old when I set a childhood philosophy – knowledge, power, and authority are vested in adults. Their words were the absolute but subjective truth. Yet, no matter how subjective it is, I had to trust them.

Life in a different home – with my sister, aunt, and uncle – has become so bearable that I forgot my mom and enjoyed life in the process of learning something new. But just when I learned to accept life's reality, mom returned home. I was in grade school then. No explanation. No apology. If my memory serves me right, months after her return, dad appeared. There was neither an explanation nor an apology either. It was a sad truth, a bitter sweet memory, and a heart-breaking sunshine to a 5-year-old.

Life's ironies

I thought everything would be fine after having my parents reconciled. Until one day my mom broke off her plans. "I'll have to go to Manila. I got a work and a business partnership with my cousin," she started. Dad negated but failed to win in their argument. I was in my fourth grade when I started seeing dad's true color – a drunkard and gambler but had his bible studies when he was young. He was very concerned with education but he had me stop my studies because I was poor at math and failed in it. My math teacher, whose name I do not even know because we never met, failed me in the subject. She was on maternity leave from the start of the school year for two months. When she returned, she reviewed the class for one week because the following week was set for examination. I was not around because I got sick for the entire week. Report grades were given, and boom! I failed. Dad physically abused me because of it. I was a shame to the family. From this experience, I learned that teachers are political in nature. They control the authority. They hold in their hands the future of the learners. I never dreamt of becoming one. It was a profession I dreaded the most.

When dad lashed me with words and stick and belt, I left home. Every day was a torture. It was not a home for me. It was a hell with its king in it. I went back to my childless aunt. I had no plans of finishing my studies. I just wanted to breathe – to live. I felt like I had no competence, no future, no life.

Education

I enrolled in a different school determined to prove to my father that I could do things he never expected from me. Fortunately, I ranked first when I was a freshman in high school and was transferred to the most brilliant class the following years and excelled in English and other subjects other than math. On this account, I could tell that the 'system' may not have been 'activated' for one reason or another and, consequently, I was not able to perform the act the statement of competence specified. Chomsky thinks that this account is essential in order to account for the creativity of human linguistic ability, which involves understanding and producing sentences never previously encountered. This account ignores the plasticity of human ability. Competence in the ordinary sense involves performance in circumstances that, although normal, are almost always novel. Our abilities to swim, drive motorcycles, etc. are constantly exercised in novel conditions without its ever being presupposed that we need an innate neural representational system for swimming or driving in order to carry them out. In my case, everything seemed to be novel in every mathematical situation. I felt like I was deceived to have been chosen as a Math Challenger when I was in grade six. But I realized, later on, that learning is a process and is developmental. Development is closely linked with learning, and, although the relationship between the two is far from clear, it is connected with the fact that humans grow from babies into

adults. There are two kinds of educational development theory. The first is a normative account of how education should proceed through consecutive stages (Egan 1986; Whitehead 1967). The second postulates that the human mind grows through distinct stages at which different kinds of learning take place. Maybe I developed my mind later than others. I truly believe that every learner is unique and smart but s/he has to continue discovering his/her inner potentials.

In my high school days, never had I ever studied at home because my aunt restricted me (I am supposed to learn at school so it would be so stupid of me to study again at home, she said). There was even a time that I prepared materials (visual aids) for my class report and she got angry, “*unya, ma- valedictorian na ka ana?*” (Would you become valedictorian now that you are doing that?) It was both a question and an insult that I brought with me everywhere in my learning journey. I moved from one school year to another with rewards but without studying anything. My technique was simple. Listening. I listened attentively to teachers and tried understanding everything there was to understand. My aunt did not give much attention to my performance at school, to rewards, and to anything so I was not able to experience receiving my medals or awards every after-school year. My rewards did not amount to their time. I kept the information to myself and did not tell them. High school years were the best years for many, but it was the other way around for me. I felt like I was caged. I could not even go outside if not for my studies, or for the lack of household’s needs. Curiosity pushed me to ask my aunt about it – why can’t I go out, why should I stay home, and all the whys I could think of. I received an answer that satisfied all my questions and confusions – she doesn’t want me to become just like her. She said she was once like me – freely enjoying her life outside with her friends. But she got raped and got pregnant earlier than planned. The answer was like a bomb to me. It exploded without prior warning but answers all my inner queries. From her answer came my ‘that’s whys’. So that was why she allowed me to be visited by my friends rather than me to my friends and classmates. She allowed my friends to sleep over in the house rather than me to theirs. She restricted me from going outside and discover something that could be destructive to me and to my future. It was in that answer that I learned her truest and purest intention. It was a crying moment for both of us. She freed herself from that nightmare and I freed myself from questions and from the feeling of being disadvantaged.

One day, when I went home from school, I received a news that turned my life upside down in some ways. It was about dad’s death. He got shot seven times and wounded on the same spots. Some said it was because dad spoke English the whole time he was drinking with his peers – friends, cousins, nephews. Some said the offender already had issues with him. Whatever the true reason was, I still felt a pang of pain. I regretted losing him without even knowing him more. He was a wise man to many and I wanted to know more of his wisdom. But it was already too late for me. At first, I was not really affected of his passing. I sang songs and acted like it was just an ordinary and normal day with ordinary news too. I even prepared myself for school the following day. Had it not for my aunt, I couldn’t be seen in the wake. I still went to school the following day to inform the principal of dad’s passing and that I had to be absent for some time. I saw my principal’s shocked expression, and my teachers’ disbelief. They then talked about dad’s contribution to the school from planning to implementation of school policies. From there I learned that he was more than the person I knew. That was the first time I cried over dad’s death but I hid it from my friends, classmates, and family. I returned home with a heavy heart. After the burial, the family decided to have me continue my studies in Iligan City to keep us all from more deaths. The offender let loose of his words that he’d kill us all. He was my mother’s cousin that was why I couldn’t fathom his reasons and anger to my father.

Freedom

The environment that I grow up in is a smorgasbord of everything. I was born to *Grace-believer* (Protestantism) parents but was partly raised in a catholic-oriented family. Living with catholic people around me has never been a problem to me because we understand and respect each other's beliefs. My lolo and aunt were deeply in to Catholicism while my uncle believed (*now, not anymore*) in the teachings of *Iglesia ni Cristo* (Church of Christ). I, on the other hand, believe in the grace that was preached by Apostle Paul. Usually, every Sunday, we go on separate ways. Funny but we don't argue on this. I remember when I was a child, I got asked by everyone at home on what I learned from church and we share to each other everything we've learned. From this set up, I learned the value of respect for one's faith. Every time my friends and classmates are arguing about their faith, I just kept silent while listening to them. For me, trying to win in an argument that has been a debate since time immemorial is such a waste of time and energy. Plus, we can lose some friends in the process. Sometimes, really, silence is the ultimate answer to an argument.

Speaking of silence, I remember myself being so silent every time my parents or any adult was asking me especially when I got accused of doing something I didn't really do. For me, defending myself would be futile when their minds are already set into what they believed was right. That was so childish of me. I did not realize that speaking up could also change their minds. I just chose silence to avoid further fights or arguments or whatever you call it. At this age, I still have a part of this attitude – keeping silent to avoid fights. When I was in college, I got scared. People expect too much from me – my teachers, my parents, my foster parents, and even my friends. So, after graduation I immediately fled from home, settled somewhere far from these people, and worked in a company for years. I did not have any plan of taking the licensure exam for fear of flunking it. Only when my sister and my high school principal pushed me to take it that I did it. Fortunately, I passed and didn't fail the people around me even without any review. It somehow helped me get over my fears. I started learning to trust myself.

From these experiences, I can remember Dewey's words about the environment – that it consists of the sum total of conditions which are concerned in the execution of the activity characteristic of a person. The social environment consists of all the activities of fellow beings that are bound up in the carrying on of the activities of any one of its members. It is truly educative in its effect in the degree in which an individual shares or participates in some conjoint activity. I lived with my aunt, uncle, and *lolo* since I was young. From them, I learned so much about life and living; about growing, and striving – almost everything in life.

Growth

Growing from oppressive social and intellectual climate took some time for me. It required my uncompromising steadfastness in my personal and intellectual beliefs, and consumed too much of my strength and courage.

Back when I was a curious youth, I thought everything would be fine if I get to finish a degree and get a work that I love. Now, I realize how wrong I was. Life is a never-ending search for something that meets human satisfaction. It is not just about the knowledge you get from school. It is also about how well you live for and with others. This made me remember Nietzsche's statement that life is more important than distanced knowledge. But through education – formal and experiences, I grow from being naïve and plain to being mature, understanding and critical in everything that's happening around me. It's a whole new feeling to know something and be able to share the same knowledge to those who need it most.

Hence, knowledge is not something you are born with. It is something you learned from people and everything around you and in most cases, we call them teachers. Experiences, people, and other circumstances make us the person we want to be and supposed to become.

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